

rice soil, we mixed 5 ml or 10 ml of the fertilizer solution corresponding to 250 mg and 500 mg N/ pot, or 100 and 200 kg N/ ha. A clay pot with no applied N was the control. Treatments were replicated seven times, with one pot as a replication.

Three 7-d-old seedlings were transplanted in each pot. At 20 d after transplanting (DT), potted plants were covered with mylar film cages and infested with 20 newly hatched BPH nymphs per cage. After 18 d, or when insects reached adulthood, all but 3 pair (male and female, randomly selected) of BPH were removed. The six were left to develop a population in each cage. The insects removed from the cages were collected in vials, oven dried, and individually weighed. Because survival on IR60 was very low, no weights were

recorded. For the population growth test, BPH reared on IR26 plants in a separate cage were used to reinfest IR60 at 3 pair/ cage.

To determine the effect of BPH feeding rate at different N levels, one seedling was planted in a clay pot. At 30 DT, we recorded honeydew excretion (mm^2) by 5 adult females on filter paper treated with bromocresol green.

BPH weight (Fig. 1), feeding rate, and population growth (Fig. 2) increased with N application on IR26, Utri Rajapan, and Triveni. Population growth on IR26 and Utri Rajapan, without antibiotics, increased threefold with added N, and twofold on moderately resistant Triveni (Fig. 2). On IR26, Utri Rajapan, and Triveni, weight per female increased at both 250 and 500 mg N/ pot. Although IR60 was

2. BPH population development on selected varieties grown under different N fertilizer rates, IRRI.

highly resistant at the high N level and the BPH number remained low, the population doubled with applied N. \mathcal{L}

Insecticides to control thrips and caseworm in rice nurseries

S. Uthamasamy, S. Suresh, and A. A. Kareem, Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute, Aduthurai 612101, India

Thrips *Stenchaetothrips biformis* (Bagnell) and caseworm *Nymphula depunctalis* (Guen.) severely damage rice seedlings. We evaluated seed treatment and soil application of insecticides before and after sowing for their

control. CR1009 was planted in 4-m² plots. Thrips population was recorded on 10 randomly chosen seedlings/ plot at 20 and 30 d after sowing (DAS). At 30 DAS, percent caseworm damage was recorded for 10 seedlings/ plot based on total leaves and damaged leaves.

Broadcasting carbofuran 3 G at 0.5 kg ai/ ha before sowing and at 10 DAS controlled thrips most effectively. Broadcasting carbofuran at 10 DAS controlled caseworm most effectively (see table). \mathcal{L}

Insect pests of early season rice nurseries in the Imphal Valley

R. N. Barwal, Indian Council of Agricultural Research (ICAR) Complex for NEH Region, Bishnupur, Shillong 793013, India; and A. C. Sharma and K. V. P. Rao, ICAR Complex, Manipur Centre, Imphal 795001, India

In the Imphal Valley, cold weather prevents germination of rice seed in Feb

Varietal response to root aphid *Rhopalosiphum rufiabdominalis* (Sasaki) in winter rice nurseries, Imphal, India.

Variety	Aphid burns	
	No.	Area ^a (%)
Prasad (IR1561-2166)	8a	2 (7.99)
Punshi (IR661-1-140-3-2/Phouren)	8 ab	2 (7.87)
P-33 (TNI/Basmati 370)/(Ratna)	9ab	3 (9.13)
RCM-1 (Moirangphou/Jaya)	11 b	4 (11.06)
CH-1039	17 c	8 (16.52)
CD (P=0.05)	3	3

^a Values in the parentheses are arc sin percent transformation. Means followed by a common letter are not significantly different.

Control of thrips and caseworm in rice nurseries, Tamil Nadu, India, 1984. ^a

Treatment	Thrips (no./seedling)		Caseworm (% damaged leaves) 30 DAS
	20 DAS	30 DAS	
Seed soaking ^b in chlorpyrifos, 0.2% for 3 h	0.5 c	0.9 bcd	12.0 b
Seed soaking ^b in chlorpyrifos, 0.1% for 3 h	0.4 bc	0.8 abcd	15.0 bc
Broadcasting carbofuran 3 G, 0.5 kg ai/ ha before sowing	0.1 a	0.4 ab	10.3 ab
Broadcasting phorate 10 G, 1.0 kg ai/ ha before sowing	0.2 ab	1.2 cd	12.3 b
Broadcasting carbofuran 3 G, 0.5 kg ai/ ha at 10 DAS	0.2 ab	0.3 a	4.8 a
Broadcasting phorate 10 G, 1.0 kg ai/ ha at 10 DAS	0.2 ab	0.6 abc	19.0 c
Untreated check	0.4 bc	1.3 d	13.5 bc
CD (0.05)	0.3	0.5	5.6

^a Values are means of 4 replications. DAS = days after sowing. Means in a column followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level. ^b 12 ml (0.2%) and 6 ml (0.1%) of chlorpyrifos 20 EC used in 1.2 liters of water for soaking 1.0 kg seed.